

CARGO ON INTERNATIONAL HIGHWAYS REST AREAS FOR CARS

Nurdinov M.¹

¹associate professor, Department of Vehicle engineering,
Andijan Machine-Building Institute.

G'anijonov M.²

²student Andijan Machine-Building Institute

Abdupattoyev B.³

³student Andijan Machine-Building Institute

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Today, on the highways of international importance located in the territory of our Republic (there are 35 highways of international importance), there is a shortage of parking places for international trucks, their distance is long or there is no parking at all. This situation can be attributed to the increase in the process of automobileization in the republic, the increase in the volume of global cargo transportation in the process of globalization, and as a result, the level of loading of international highways has increased. In addition, it is possible to cite the fact that there are insufficiently organized parking spaces on international roads in our republic, and that work in this regard is now being planned [1]. At the same time, the development of the road sector is becoming one of the most important tasks in our republic today. In this regard, in the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, including "...implementation of targeted programs for the development and modernization of road transport, engineering-communication and social infrastructure,..." task is defined. In this regard, road construction and modernization of roads are being carried out at a rapid pace in the country. In the next three years, 9.8 trillion soums were allocated by the state for road construction[2].

If we look at the world statistics on automobiles, the number of cars in the world is more than 1.3 million. This indicator is increasing by 3.9% per year [3]. According to the accounting books, the number of cars on the planet will increase by another 1.2 million in the next 30 years, and it is noted that this figure mainly corresponds to the regions of Asia and the Pacific Ocean.[4].

Of course, one of the most important problems related to the increase in cars is the lack of parking spaces in city centers. In Stockholm, Sweden, approximately 15% of city streets are used for parked vehicles.[5].

Parking for trucks - (international experience) where
is the best place to park for trucks

Only in movies they show how truck drivers rent a hotel room, in real life there is no price for such a vacation, so you can often see several cars parked next to

the traffic police post. Semi-trailers carry valuable cargo, so sometimes truckers block the back doors and block the trucks.

Well-maintained truck stops along the highway are still a rarity for Russian roads, but changes for the better are already visible.

To the parking lot for trucks
general requirements

Trucks with a total mass of more than 3.5 tons are prohibited from parking in settlements outside of specially equipped areas, but in small towns parking for trucks is still rare, at best there is a dirty place at the entrance without lighting. These types of vehicles include MAN truck tractor, VOLVO semi-trailer, Scania R 440 truck tractor, flatbed semi-trailer [6].

The current regulations stipulate that there should be a special sign at the parking lot for trucks - a silhouette of a truck with its weight.

Special areas are starting to appear along major highways and highways, where each stop has the following dimensions:

Figure 1. The parking lot is located at an angle of 45° to the road

length / width - 14–22 / 3.5–5 m;

passage width from 5.5 to 12 m.

Parking lots must have entrance/exit signs and signs.

Standards and security levels

The size of the parking space for any cargo and trucks is calculated depending on the dimensions and installation method, for example:

Perpendicular to the road - this option is considered the most economical. The area of one parking space is 50.7 square meters. meters, length and depth - 13 m, width - 3.9 m.

at an angle of 60 degrees. The area is 59.4 m², the length / depth is similar to the first point, but the dimensions should be increased along the passage.

45 degrees on the road. The area was increased to 65.4 square meters. m, the depth decreases - 11.9 m, and the size along the passage increases - 5.5 m. parallel placement. One parking space is allocated 66.3 m², length - 17 m, depth and width - 3.9 m.

Figure 2. Parallel parking at 15° to the road.

The minimum area in the first option is 66.3 m² when placing cars with a length of more than 12 m.

Figure 3. Perpendicular parking at an angle of 30° to the road.

Special parking spaces for buses and trucks are being equipped along the highways, so that truckers will be able to park their vehicles with all the conveniences, instead of on the side of the road, as was the case before. [7]. Many parking lots are located near motels and roadside cafes where drivers can enjoy a good meal and relax in well-appointed rooms.

On such sites, marking is conditional or absent at all, since the dimensions of the cargo are significantly different from each other. The dimensions of the parking lot depend on the estimated number of cars, but must comply with the parameters indicated in the previous section [8].

The best option is asphalt, but gravel is also good, especially in winter, because it eliminates slipping during ice. The parking lot should be lit and there should be no dark areas. Unfortunately, trucks can only dream of such comfort on many roads.

It is easy to find parking spaces for Euro trucks abroad, the size of the site is standard, but they are distinguished by excellent lighting, security and other advantages of civilization. Availability is indicated by a route planner such as DKV MAPS or DKV APP, where the driver can find the nearest free parking spaces for trucks [9].

How to choose a place for a car

Trucks visually choose a place to rest, and if they have already traveled along the route, they use the experience of past stops. But for the convenience of drivers of long-haul flights, Cargolink Parking and Geo-Chats application appeared.

With the help of this convenient option, more than 8,000 trucks on the roads of the CIS and European countries were able to quickly find guarded parking lots with ATMs, shops, cheap cafes with Wi-Fi. as a gas station and first aid station.

Drivers who use the application leave their impressions, as a result, it turns out that every third parking space of 7.15 thousand parking lots located in the CIS (data at the end of 2016) has a positive rating.

Obligations of drivers.

For every driver, understanding the rules of the road and the special conditions of driving on roads in different regions of the Russian Federation is the basis for their work.

Also, the freight forwarder must know and fulfill the following obligations:

filling out invoices correctly;

securely fasten the load inside the semi-trailer;

to be in constant contact with the dispatcher of the firm or company that owns the cargo and not only to deliver the cargo from the city to a specific place indicated in the additional documents;

shipping represents the company to some extent, so suppliers may ask questions about the cargo being transported;

The vehicle must be returned to the place of registration in good condition, if it is necessary to replace parts, you must contact your supervisor directly, for example, rolling stock.

What can be fined

It may be considered a violation if a driver leaves a truck or a car in a place that does not meet the requirements of traffic rules, and a fine is imposed for a truck parked along the road near a residential area at night. [10].

From November 1, 2019, the following sanctions will come into force:

drivers of trucks and buses are prohibited from driving a vehicle for more than 9 hours a day, they must change partners to rest after 4.5 hours;

tachometers will be installed on all trucks with a mass of more than 3.5 tons from 11.01.19 to monitor performance;

if necessary, it is allowed to drive the vehicle for up to 10 hours, but no more than twice in a week;

total driving time during the week - 56, and for two - 90 hours;

The Code of Administrative Offenses sets fines in the amount of 1-5 thousand rubles for drivers, 7-10 thousand rubles for officials, and 20-50 thousand rubles for legal entities and is approved by the State Duma;

parking of trucks is allowed only in specially equipped places equipped with night lighting, in addition, you must place the following: toilet, security room, fire extinguishing equipment.

In European countries, such bans have existed for many years, but every 50-60 km there are parking lots for trucks equipped with everything necessary for quality rest. Currently, there is no such service on Russian roads, so hundreds of thousands of drivers can become potential violators.

Figure 4. Parking lots located in Europe

Figure 5. Trucks located in Europe

Parking search system for

In Western Europe, parking lots for trucks have long been considered and served as an example, but now the situation has changed radically, so drivers of heavy vehicles should be especially careful [11].

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